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GIS-BASED ANALYSIS OF SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF ELECTRICITY TRANSFORMERS IN SOME PARTS OF RIGASA, IGABI L.G.A

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Abstract

Abstract: This paper analyzed the spatial distribution of electricity transformers in Taro-Taro, Makera, and Hayin Dangaladima Rigasa, Igabi L.G.A. QGIS 3.18 software was used for data processing and analysis. The geographic location of transformers was acquired using GPS and displayed in the QGIS environment which appeared as a point layer on the map showing the attributes tables of the transformers. In view of this study, nineteen electric transformers in Taro-Taro and Makera/Hayin Dangaladima were examined. The pattern of distribution of electric transformers in the Taro-Taro and Makera/Hayin Dangaladima is that the electric transformers are dispersed. The facilities in the electric transformers were also examined, where the 500KVA transformer has the highest number, while the 200KVA, which is only one, has the least number in terms of capacity. Five electric transformers with ten years of service have the highest with 26.32%, and four electric transformers each with one year, two years, eight years, and 12 years of service have the lowest with 5.26% This study reveals the ability of GIS and remote sensing techniques to capture and acquire spatiotemporal data for analyzing the distribution of electricity transformers. Kaduna Electricity Distribution Company should as a matter of urgency come to the aid of this community to improve and increase the number of transformers that require replacement and those that require upgrading.

Keywords: Spatial distribution, Transformers, Electricity, GIS

INTRODUCTION

The electric power sector is one of the most important elements within the broader energy framework. Fortunately, demand analyses and load forecasts for this sector have a better foundation than those of other energy sources because of the availability of accurate consumption data from individually metered customers, although such data may not always be available in a convenient format, for analytical purposes (Munasinghe, 1990). The Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) formerly known as the National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) is an organization involved in the supply of electricity in Nigeria and presently due to privatization of the power

sector, Kaduna, Zamfara, Kebbi, and Sokoto states now has an electricity distribution power body called Kaduna Electricity Distribution Company (Kaduna Electric). The power sector plays a very important role in the economic development of a nation; therefore, the growth of industries, agriculture, infrastructure, and the private sector is dependent on the state of the power sector (Abana, 2018).

Electric power is the engine that drives industrialization, which improves communication, helps innovation in science and Technology, provides sound healthcare delivery system and improves citizen's standard of living. Since electric power is the engine that drives industrialization, a stable

supply is the key for Nigeria to become one of the 20 developed economies in the world (Baba et al., 2020). However, it is unfortunate that the biggest problem in Nigeria is the electricity crisis, a crisis without end. However, the electricity supply in Nigeria is characterized by frequent power failures and load shedding (Kareem, 2006).

Generally, electricity could be accepted as an electric current. This involves generation, transmission and distribution of the electric current to consumers. Electricity is an aspect of the utility sector that is very essential to the smooth and meaningful development of a society. It supports the economy and promotes the well-being of individuals. The efficient functioning of this utility is of paramount importance for the sustenance of its growth and the consequential realization of its planning and managerial objectives (Emengini, 2004). According to Arunagiri and Agarwal (2005), distributing transformers can also be fitted with meters so that loading of the transformers can be monitored in a real-time and the need for new transformers can be decided. This can be made visual by assigning a different colour on the map for a transformer once it is overloaded, hence giving a proper warning. Any aberration can be easily detected (Chatta 2011).

Transformers are not evenly distributed in Nigeria and as a result of that, the rate of the utilization of each one may be high. Due to the fact that a lot of houses use just one transformer which will in turn make the transformers to develop problems and at the end even pack up. An example is the case where there is one transformer serving many houses beyond its capacity that transformer may pack up due to the excess load it is carrying. Energy demand in developing countries will rise enormously as per capita incomes and population grows. No country has been able to raise per capita income from low levels to high levels without increasing its use

of commercial energy. Modern energy forms have been proven to have raised the economic output of many countries in the world (Anderson, 1997). Sule (2015) also reported that the distribution areas in Kaduna, Kebbi and Sokoto have been completed but are yet to be commissioned and once commissioned they will add to what the states are receiving from the distribution company and that will boost power supply in the zone.

With regard to the above-highlighted challenges facing power sectors as well as the current reforms aimed at mitigating the challenges, this study therefore can be considered timely and relevant as it is meant to improve the understanding of electricity power distribution effective power supply. Most importantly, it will help the power industry to keep track of the electrical facilities (transformers) involved in the delivery of energy to the end-users. This was made possible with the aid of geodatabase management system, as variety of information can be better organized on a computer system linking the database to an output map and is effectively used to manage and monitor information on the distribution of electricity to end-users including information describing their spatial and non-spatial attributes such as geographical location and transformer capacity in KVA.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area is situated between Latitudes 10° 31' 30.14, 10° 32' 53.62 N of the equator, and Longitudes 7° 22' 33.88, 7° 23' 45.02 E, of the Greenwich meridian. The study area is located in Kaduna metropolis which is the capital city of Kaduna State in Northern Nigeria. It covers mainly some localities within Igabi local government area. The study is restricted to Taro-taro and Makera/Hayin Dangeladima Rigasa, Igaba L.G.A.

Figure 1: Map of The Study Area

Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

Reconnaissance Survey

A reconnaissance survey was conducted to familiarize with the study area. This gave the researchers an in-depth knowledge of the electricity distribution and condition transformer in the study area.

Data

The administrative map of Taro-Taro and Makera/Hayin Dungaladima was obtained from GRID3 Nigeria. The geographical coordinates of the electricity transformers were obtained using a Garmin 60CSx handheld GPS receiver, these geographic locations were used to create a map showing the various locations of the electricity transformers with the aid of a technical staff from Kaduna Electricity

Distribution Company. Lastly, the names of substations, capacity, condition, ownership and year of service of the electricity transformers.

Data Processing

Data obtained were processed and analyzed as follows based on the research objectives. This study used QGIS 3.18 software for data processing and analysis. Thus, all datasets were transformed into ESRI format (shape files). The administrative map of Taro-Taro and Makera/Hayin Dungaladima was projected to UTM Zone 32 N using a shape file was created for all features of interest such as the location of electricity transformers is represented as points, and roads were represented with lines and administrative

boundaries with polygons. The geographical location of transformers was acquired using GPS and transformed into plain text file format in Microsoft Excel and was imported into the QGIS environment as waypoints which appeared as points layer on the map showing the attributes tables of the transformers. The pattern of distribution of transformers was determined using the Average Nearest Neighbour (NN) statistical tool. The tool measures the distance between each feature and

its nearest Neighbour's location. It then averaged all these nearest Neighbour distances. Based on the attributes derived from the administration of the questionnaire, a database was created using Microsoft Access and QGIS software. The data for each transformer was entered into its attribute table. The table created in Microsoft Access was exported as CSV file format which was compatible with QGIS. The tables were imported into the QGIS environment for analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2: Spatial Distribution of Electric Transformers

Source: Authors' Analysis, 2023

Spatial Pattern of Electric Transformer

The distribution pattern of electric transformers in the study area was determined by the Average Nearest Neighbour on ArcGIS 10.3 software. The average nearest neighbour analysis calculates the nearest neighbour index, which is a measure of the distance between each facility centroid and its nearest neighbour's centroid location; it then averages all these nearest neighbour distances. According to Getis and Ord (1998), the z-score usually returns a range of values between -2.58 to 2.58; therefore, a negative z-score less than -

2.58 indicates a significant clustering at the 0.01 probability level. A range of scores between both 2.58 to -1.96 at 0.05 significant level and -1.96 to -1.65 at 0.10 probability level shows that there is a tendency towards a clustered pattern. A range of z-scores between -1.65 to 1.65 indicates a random distribution. Again, if the z-score lies between both 1.65 to 1.95 at the 0.10 significance level and 1.96 to 2.58 at the 0.05 probability level then it is obvious that there is a tendency towards a regular pattern.

Figure 3: Spatial pattern of electric transformers

Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

Table 1: Average Nearest Neighbor Summary

Observed Mean Distance	329.8690 m
Expected Mean Distance	248.9263 m
Nearest Neighbor Ratio:	1.325168
Z-score	2.639213
p-value	0.008310

Looking at the Nearest Neighbor Ratio of 1.325168 with critical value (z-score) of 2.639213 at 0.008310 level of significance (p-value) in Table 1 and the pattern of distribution in Figure 2, it can be concluded that the pattern of distribution of electric transformers in the Taro-Taro and Makera/Hayin Dangladima is that the public electric transformers are dispersed around each other and around those areas where services are available.

Figure 4: Capacity of Transformers

Sources: Authors analysis 2023

Table 2: Capacity of transformer in percentage

S/No	Capacity	Number	%
1	200kva	1	5.26
2	300kva	5	26.32
3	500kva	13	68.42
4	Total	19	100

From Table 2, it was observed that 200KVA transformers were only one in number, which amounted to 5.26%, while 300KVA transformers were five in number and accounted for 26.32% of the study area. While 500KVA transformers were thirteen in number and accounted for 68.42% of the study area. In summary, the 500KVA transformer has the highest number while the 200KVA, which is only one, has the least number. Figure 4 shows how the spatial distribution of capacity of the transformers is being distributed. 200KVA, which is identified in red, is located in the northern part of the study area. While the 300KVA, which is in yellow, is located in the northern part and southern part of the study area. The third, which is the 500KVA, is green in color and is located in the northwest, southern part and southeast of the study area.

CONCLUSION

The research work reveals the ability of GIS and remote sensing techniques to capture and acquiring spatial data for analyzing the distribution of electricity transformers, their locations, the average transformers requiring upgrading, those requiring total replacement and the ones required to be a relief to enable safeguard the networks and enable prevent the occurrence of electrical facilities damage, life and property prevention. More so, to improve the living condition of the society, through socio and economic activities. Furthermore, based on the acknowledged analysis and the degree of various data acquired, reference to

the area of the research, the study has identified that the Kaduna Electricity Distribution Company (Kaduna Electric) should do as a matter of urgency to come to the aid of this community to improve and increase the level of their income to their company.

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